

The Coupling Constant Series and Magnetic Monopoles – 8 Theory

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Abstract:

By analyzing the new framework, 8T, and the insights gain regarding the nature of the electron as the majestic (3) in the coupling term describing the Electric, it is possible to reason why there could not be magnetic monopoles in nature. The argument is constructed upon symmetry and vanishing of spinning charges in a large cluster of variation elements.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (0)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (2)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \bigoplus (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Primes set} \quad (2.1)$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \bigoplus (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P} \quad (2.2)$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (2.3)$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ...$$

Examine the term describing the electric coupling. We proved majestic (3) is the electron in the 8-Theory thesis.

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + 5 \quad (2.31)$$

Define a magnet as a set of electrons, which spin around as part of a larger cluster of matter.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N e_i \rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^N (3)_i \quad (2.32)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N e_i \in \sum_{k=1}^M \delta g_k ; M > N \quad (2.33)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^M \delta g_k = 0 \quad (2.34)$$

As we did in the 8T thesis, the elements in the term describing matter anti commute, appear in an even number that differ in sign and vanish to zero when summed. However, the spinning electrons are added to a positive summation:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N (3)_i > 0 \quad (2.35)$$

We have two conditions that are not aligned and contradict each other. Both were proven in the 8-Theory to be correct.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N (3)_i > 0 \cap \sum_{k=1}^M \delta g_k = 0 \quad (2.36)$$

The only way to satisfy the second term is to add an opposite spinning cluster so the term would vanish into zero, meaning spinning cluster of electrons in the opposite direction, so (2.34) would be satisfied.

$$\sum_{i=1}^T (-3)_i < 0 \quad (2.37)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^T (-3)_i + \sum_{i=1}^N (3)_i = 0; \quad T = N \quad (2.38)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^M \delta g_k = 0 \quad (2.34)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)